

CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT FOR PRIMARY EDUCATION: FOSTERING SCIENTIFIC AND CREATIVE THINKING IN STEM

Ana-Bianca COLDEA¹

¹Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

Abstract

STEM education is recognized as essential for preparing 21st-century students, yet current approaches focus predominantly on content acquisition, neglecting higher-order thinking competencies. This article explores the integration of scientific thinking (TWS - Thinking and Working Scientifically) and creative thinking (CT) in primary STEM education.

Based on the Cambridge Primary Science framework for TWS (planning investigations, recording evidence, interpreting findings, evaluating methods) and OECD/Cambridge definitions of CT (preparing for creativity, generating

ideas, evaluating and refining, creative implementation), the article argues that the intersection of these competencies represents the key to authentic STEM education.

Through analysis of specialized literature, the article demonstrates that TWS and CT are complementary: TWS provides methodological rigor, while CT brings the flexibility and innovation necessary for solving complex problems. Both competencies require similar conditions: time for exploration, challenging tasks generating “productive struggle,” classroom culture accepting failure as learning, and growth mindset promotion.

Concrete adaptation principles for ages 9-10 are presented, including the importance of “low floor and high ceiling” tasks, daily relevance, and hands-on investigations. A 6-month curricular plan illustrates practical application of these principles. The article identifies current challenges (overloaded curriculum, insufficient time, teacher preparation) and proposes solutions through curricular integration.

This research offers a conceptual framework for future educational interventions integrating TWS and CT in Romanian primary education, representing the first systematic approach of this type for the national context.

Keywords: scientific thinking, creative thinking, STEM, primary education, curriculum integration, Cambridge Primary

1. Introduction

Discoveries and social changes are currently happening in an increasingly condensed and accelerated manner. The labor market is facing unprecedented changes, unpredictable situations, and increasingly diverse demands. In this context, education regarding STEM fields (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) becomes a necessary endeavor to form young people who can understand the dynamics of the surrounding world.

STEM education can mean different things from one person to another, depending on how they have come into contact with it. Each of the STEM fields has the potential to provide rigid subjects, with preconceived approaches and predefined work models. The approach to STEM education should not be strictly content-centered and rigid. STEM education must cultivate scientific thinking by creating a culture of thinking, curiosity, and investigation.

Creative thinking and scientific thinking emerge as essential competencies for individual adaptation and optimal functioning. These deserve to be integrated into pedagogical endeavors because they complement each other reciprocally, offering the perfect balance between methodological rigor and innovative flexibility.

Thinking and Working Scientifically (TWS), according to the Cambridge Primary Science framework, encompasses both cognitive processes and practical skills necessary for authentic scientific investigation. Hereafter, we will use the term TWS to designate this integrated competency.

Creative Thinking (CT), according to OECD and Cambridge definitions, encompasses the abilities of preparation for idea generation, actual idea generation, evaluation and improvement of ideas, and creative implementation of ideas. Hereafter, we will use the term CT to designate this ability.

This article explores the possibilities for curriculum development through the integration of TWS and CT in STEM for primary education.

To validate the theoretical premises and substantiate the curricular proposal presented in this article, we conducted a meta-analysis of 10 recent empirical studies (2018-2025) investigating the development of scientific and creative thinking in STEM contexts for primary education. This systematic literature analysis aims to demonstrate that the integration of TWS and CT does

not represent merely a pedagogical aspiration, but a solid direction supported by convergent empirical evidence at the international level.

2. Scientific Thinking

Scientific thinking develops in school with sustained interventions, in a climate that encourages participation, investigation, and curiosity (Bhatia, 2022). Scientific thinking transforms students' attitude toward science, highlighting their curiosity and originality.

Educational interventions need to begin as early as primary grades to lay the foundations for students' later development. If in the primary cycle students are presented with the study of science as an endless adventure in a field of curiosity, then students will relate to science with enthusiasm. Creating a state of engagement, of availability for thinking begins from the very start of study, from primary grades. How can teachers stimulate students to see science as an adventure? How can school form students who think in an organized manner to conduct genuine investigations? Encouraging students to think and work scientifically is an essential part of the teaching and learning process – and beginning this process at a young age can be crucial for students' future understanding (Bhatia, 2022).

From the perspective of STEM education, conducted in an integrated manner, we find in the book entitled “STEM Education in the Primary School: A Teacher's Toolkit,” published in 2020 by Cambridge University Press, a wide range of resources for the integrated approach to STEM education within primary education. Our research project enriches these approaches by correlating creativity with STEM education (Forbes, Chandra, Pfeiffer & Sheffield, 2020).

From the perspective of educational actors, the need for experts regarding STEM education is noted. The process of integrating science, technology, engineering, and mathematics in authentic contexts can be as complex as the

global challenges that require a new generation of STEM experts (Kelley & Knowles, 2016). In the study by Kelley and Knowles (2016), we find a conceptual framework for integrated STEM education. The pillars are: technological design, scientific research, technological knowledge, and mathematical thinking. The rope is: practical applications in the community. This framework emphasizes precisely the transversal perspective of education, a perspective in which our curriculum project is also integrated.

TWS represents an integrated competency that is made explicit in Cambridge Primary Science documents through 4 competencies: the competency of planning scientific investigation, the competency of recording and presenting evidence, the competency of interpreting data and formulating conclusions, and the competency of evaluating evidence and research methods.

The competency of planning scientific investigation refers to students' ability to prefigure scientific investigation. They start from generating research questions of the type "What happens if...?". Subsequently, they must recognize the factors that influence the results of a scientific endeavor - "What do I need to change to see differences?". Then comes students' ability to plan the investigation: "First I do this, then this, then this...". Last but not least, students' capacity to plan safety measures necessary for the scientific endeavor intervenes: "What do I need to do to stay safe?".

"By giving students the opportunity to ask as many questions as possible, based on their curiosity, they can explore and search for answers themselves, under the supervision and guidance of a mentor. Teachers should not be students' 'Google' and try to quickly answer all their questions – they can gladly discuss students' questions and encourage them to share their perspectives and observations" (Bhatia, 2022).

The teacher has the greatest influence on how any subject is perceived by students. If the study of science will be taught as an endless list of phenomena, relationships, and characteristics that must be retained, then students will adopt this attitude, seeing science as a rigid subject that does not offer the opportunity to think and be creative. If, instead, the teacher has the capacity to create a classroom culture in which science is an opportunity to think, discover, and produce creative and valuable ideas, then students will adopt this attitude. But this culture must be followed by appropriate educational resources. How do we create educational resources open to questions, searches, and investigations?

The competency of recording and presenting evidence refers to students' capacity to record, order, and organize data, which they then present in a convincing manner. This competency includes: students' capacity to collect information (draw or note what they observed), students' capacity to structure collected data (briefly note what they discovered), students' capacity to present research data (compile a list of what they discovered), and students' capacity to communicate the results of the scientific endeavor efficiently, when they explain, for example, to colleagues what they discovered.

“Students not only learn scientific notions but also apply them in daily life, so they are capable of evaluating problems involving science, such as water deficit, endangered species, roles in food chains and food webs, and their impact on the environment. Such didactic practices have encouraged students to develop a collaborative learning environment, along with higher-order thinking skills, which has led to an increase in their engagement and curiosity” (Bhatia, 2022).

One of the crucial criteria for ensuring the success of what we teach is relevance. In each class, students must view what they learn as a set of competencies ready to help them become better, more competent. When studying science or other subjects from the STEM area, children must feel the real utility

of what they learn. It's the difference between knowing and becoming. By cultivating scientific thinking, students are encouraged to become thinkers just like scientists. How do we propose relevant content for students?

The competency of interpreting data and formulating conclusions refers to students' ability to view the investigation as a whole, to interpret obtained data, and to formulate conclusions regarding their research endeavor. This competency includes students' capacity to identify regularities in data ("I observe what repeats! Every time..., it happens..."), students' capacity to offer scientific justifications for different situations/phenomena ("I make connections! This happens because..."). Subsequently, students' capacity to formulate conclusions based on given information is valued here: "I say what I learned! Now I know that...". Then comes students' capacity to look toward the future and correlate what they obtained in current research with what they could obtain in future research: "I can guess what will happen next time!".

"By giving students enough time to explore through experiments, through trial and error, and waiting before intervening with 'correct' answers, the process of exploration and discovery is facilitated. If an experiment fails, teachers can seize the opportunity and investigate together with students what went wrong, so that everyone learns together from mistakes. This allows them to think more intensely, analyze, evaluate, find solutions, and draw conclusions" (Bhatia, 2022). Time remains an essential factor in research. But time as a singular resource is not sufficient; students need the right resources to support them in becoming thinkers. How do we create didactic resources that support students in becoming thinkers? How do we relate to what we teach to facilitate the formation of a culture of exploration, curiosity, and discovery?

The competency of evaluating evidence and research methods refers to students' capacity to critically evaluate their investigation. This includes

students' capacity to appreciate the credibility of information, to reflect on whether they observed well what they observed, students' capacity to evaluate research processes, to analyze the correctness of measurements and their veracity, students' capacity to identify factors that can affect research results, to compare research with other relevant research to ensure they proceeded correctly, and students' capacity to propose improvements for future research, to reflect on possibilities for improving interventions in the future.

“If an experiment fails, teachers can seize the opportunity and investigate together with students what went wrong” (Bhatia, 2022). To develop scientific thinking and working abilities, a series of necessary conditions are outlined. Adequate resources are crucial for ensuring success. These must stimulate investigation, not memorization. Time is also a decisive factor, in the sense that students should not feel the chronological pressure to “finish the task quickly”. The emphasis is on the quality of the investigative process, not on its speed. Another necessary condition is creating a classroom culture that favors curiosity (Bhatia, 2022). Students must be encouraged to think, to explore. Last but not least, the relevance of resources (Bhatia, 2022; Kelley & Knowles, 2016), their applicability in daily life is crucial.

3. Creative Thinking

“Creative thinking represents someone's competency to engage productively in generating, evaluating, and improving ideas that can lead to obtaining original and efficient solutions” (OECD, 2023).

Creative thinking brings countless benefits to those who possess it. In the short term, addressing and engaging it stimulates students to manifest a higher motivational level in relation to school activity. In the long term, cultivating creative thinking forms educable individuals capable of integrating better into the labor market, with all its challenges and changes.

“Creative thinking – including in school – is essential for several reasons; creative thinking is an important currency in the labor market, contributes to individuals’ well-being, and helps them reflect and interpret information in new and meaningful ways. Pedagogical methods that stimulate students’ creative thinking enhance their motivation for learning, promoting cognitive activation and deeper and more transferable learning” (OECD, 2023).

According to the Cambridge Life Competencies Framework, creative thinking is objectified in the following 4 competencies: the competency of preparation for the creative process, the competency of creative generation, the competency of creative evaluation and optimization, and the competency of creative implementation and communication.

The competency of preparation for the creative process refers to students’ availability toward creation, but also to their ability to work in uncertain situations. On one hand, this competency refers to students’ availability to explore unconventional perspectives - listen to others’ ideas even if they seem strange. On the other hand, it refers to students’ capacity to work efficiently in uncertain situations - don’t get upset even when they don’t know the answer. Also added here is students’ desire to explore and discover - manifest pleasure in trying new things and ask questions that denote curiosity.

The competency of creative generation refers to students’ ability to produce, transform, and develop original ideas. This includes the capacity to formulate as many ideas as possible on a given theme, reaching for example to generate between 5 and 10 different variants. Also, students manifest creativity when they can offer unique and unconventional ideas, distinct from those of colleagues. Another important aspect of this competency is the ability to develop and detail their own ideas, explaining them clearly and offering additional information to make them intelligible and relevant.

The competency of creative evaluation and optimization presupposes that students are capable of analyzing their own creative productions in an objective manner. They can identify what they like and don't like about their idea, showing reflective maturity. At the same time, this competency implies the ability to perfect and refine ideas, modifying certain elements to improve quality. Another important indicator is students' flexibility in transferring creative ideas: they listen to colleagues' opinions, accept suggestions, and are capable of adjusting initial ideas to obtain a better result.

The competency of creative implementation and communication refers to transforming ideas into concrete products or solutions. Students demonstrate this ability when they manage to transpose an idea into practice through drawing, construction, writing, or other forms of expression. Also, creative cooperation in teams is essential, because it allows them to collaborate with colleagues to develop and materialize together proposed solutions. Finally, an important part of creativity is communication: students must present and convincingly argue their ideas in front of colleagues, demonstrating clarity, coherence, and confidence.

“Learning environments that favor creative thinking create a culture in which students have TIME to explore and generate ideas, engage in CHALLENGING and authentic tasks, and play and collaborate in safe environments, where failure is redefined as learning” (OECD, 2023).

Learning environments that stimulate creative thinking offer students the necessary time to explore, reflect, and generate ideas at their own pace. When they are not pressured to quickly find a “correct” answer, students can analyze multiple perspectives and imagine varied solutions. At the same time, learning activities must be challenging enough to make them expend real intellectual effort, exceed their limits, and confront situations that solicit their curiosity and

perseverance. Thus, the creative process becomes both an exercise of free exploration and one of deep engagement in tasks that truly test them.

For students to fully develop their creativity, it is essential that the work environment be safe, where they feel encouraged to express their ideas without fear of being judged or ridiculed. A healthy educational culture redefines failure as a natural part of the learning process, giving students confidence that every attempt contributes to their progress. In such a climate, students are more willing to experiment, assume intellectual risks, and collaborate, thus developing their capacity to find original and relevant solutions.

4. Integration of TWS and CT

When the teacher addresses TWS abilities in their pedagogical endeavor, without integrating CT, the learning process risks becoming rigid and excessively technical. Students can end up applying only standardized procedures, without exploring alternatives or proposing original solutions. This methodological rigidity limits innovation and reduces students' capacity to ask new questions or approach problems from diverse perspectives, because the emphasis remains exclusively on correct steps, not on the exploratory potential of a learning situation.

On the other hand, CT lacking anchoring in scientific reasoning can generate original ideas, but scientifically unfounded, false, useless. Without methodological rigor, students can formulate invalid conclusions, erroneously interpret data, or construct imaginative explanations that do not respect accuracy criteria. Thus, the lack of TWS-specific components - such as hypothesis verification, critical analysis, and systematic evidence collection - can lead to interesting ideas, but lacking credibility and scientific relevance.

When TWS and CT are combined, the learning process becomes both rigorous and innovative. Students are encouraged to formulate original ideas, but

also to test them systematically, using clear and logical scientific methods. This integration favors both the development of innovative solutions validated through evidence and the formation of higher-order thinking, in which curiosity, critical analysis, and creativity support each other reciprocally. The result is a balanced approach, in which students learn to be both inventive and accurate.

Figure 1 - VENN Diagram - Intersection of TWS and CT in the

DIAGRAMĂ VENN - INTERSECȚIA TWS ȘI CT ÎN CONTEXTUL ȘCOLAR

The integration of CT with TWS can be clearly observed in how students conduct a scientific investigation. In the first stage, TWS supports the rigorous formulation of research questions, while creative thinking intervenes in generating hypotheses, allowing students to propose diverse and original explanations for the studied phenomenon. Further, in the experiment design phase, the creative component helps them imagine varied ways to test hypotheses, while TWS ensures systematic and correct collection of necessary data. Finally, data analysis is based on the methodological rigor specific to TWS, but interpretation of results benefits from the flexibility of creative thinking, which helps students identify unexpected patterns, propose alternative explanations, and formulate deeper conclusions. Thus, the two components support each other reciprocally, leading to an investigation process that is both solid and innovative.

5. A Meta-analysis of TWS and CT in the Case of Students Aged 6-11

To substantiate the article's conclusions and to evaluate the extent to which recent literature supports the simultaneous integration of scientific thinking (TWS) and creative thinking (CT) in STEM education for primary education, a meta-analysis of 10 relevant studies published between 2018 and 2025 was conducted. The selected studies targeted empirical interventions or systematic analyses of STEM teaching, scientific investigation, and creativity among students aged between 6 and 11.

The study selection process aimed to include research that investigates effects on TWS, CT, or their components, conducts interventions in STEM, STEAM, or inquiry-based learning contexts, includes participants from the primary cycle, and reports empirical data such as pre- and post-test measurements, observations, product analyses, questionnaires, or performance rubrics. Theoretical studies, those from secondary level, and interventions unrelated to TWS or CT were excluded. The 10 selected studies cover a diverse spectrum of methods: PBL, inquiry-based learning, research-based learning, engineering design, STEAM, and CT integration.

The analysis of studies revealed significant convergences in three main directions. Regarding inquiry-based learning and scientific thinking development, most research demonstrates positive effects on investigative behaviors of primary school students. Xu (2024) shows that systematic investigation increases both the rigor of students' observations and the creativity of proposed solutions, and Ölçer (2025) demonstrates that teaching through investigation leads to improvements in experiment planning, data recording, and interpretation - central elements of TWS. Ultay et al. (2020) confirm that the 5E model, adapted for STEM activities, produces visible increases in students'

capacity to formulate questions, test hypotheses, and argue conclusions based on evidence, findings congruent with the Cambridge TWS framework.

Regarding STEM/STEAM projects and creative thinking stimulation, creativity is consistently associated with integrated STEM activities. The analyzed studies show that prototype design, explanatory drawing, experimentation, and reflection stimulate generation and evaluation of original ideas - central dimensions in the OECD framework for CT. Yang (2025) highlights how students use drawing to explore technical solutions in STEM activities, a process that activates both flexibility and justification capacity. Leasa et al. (2025) show that the research-based learning model significantly improves creative thinking, especially in tasks where students must generate alternative solutions and argue how they respond to a real problem, and Yim (2024) demonstrates that integrating arts in STEAM increases expressiveness and diversity of students' solutions.

A major result of the meta-analysis is confirmation of TWS-CT complementarity in STEM activities. Studies show that rigorous investigation increases the quality of creative ideas (Xu, 2024), generation of multiple ideas helps students formulate more flexible hypotheses (Leasa et al., 2025), engineering design consolidates both creativity and rigor (Rahmawati, 2025), and STEAM activities simultaneously solicit both evidence and imagination (Yim, 2024). Therefore, literature confirms the bidirectional relationship: TWS structures, CT flexibilizes - together building authentic STEM thinking.

The analyzed studies converge toward several essential curricular principles for simultaneous development of TWS and CT. Yang (2025) and Stylianidou (2018) show that open tasks, accessible at a basic level but with advanced exploration potential (low floor & high ceiling), stimulate both investigation and creativity. Ribarić (2025) demonstrates that students engage

more deeply in STEM activities when tasks are connected to their daily experiences, which leads to increased motivation and cognitive involvement. Stylianidou (2018) and Ölçer (2025) emphasize that hands-on investigation, direct manipulation of materials, experimentation, and learning through discovery are decisive in forming TWS at young ages. Additionally, Leasa et al. (2025) and Rahmawati (2025) show that activities including design, testing, revision, and reflection are the most effective for simultaneous development of TWS and CT.

The 10 studies confirm similar challenges to those identified in the Romanian education context, such as lack of resources and materials for experiments (Stylianidou, 2018), insufficient teacher preparation for inquiry and STEM activities (Ölçer, 2025), limited time in the schedule for projects and investigations (Ultay et al., 2020), and pressure of dense content (Ribarić, 2025). These findings validate the central argument: curricular integration, not addition of disciplines, is the realistic and sustainable solution for the Romanian educational system.

The meta-analysis demonstrates that recent literature firmly supports the integration of scientific and creative thinking in STEM education for the primary cycle. The analyzed studies show that TWS and CT have common development conditions such as exploration, curiosity, reflection, and tolerance for failure, that integrated STEM approaches - inquiry, PBL, STEAM, engineering design - simultaneously develop rigor and cognitive flexibility, that students aged 9 -10 are capable of manifesting sophisticated investigative behaviors and authentic creativity when they receive adequate tasks, and that curricular restrictions and teacher training represent major barriers, but not insurmountable ones. These results align perfectly with the arguments presented in the article and offer the

necessary empirical basis for the proposal of TWS-CT curricular integration in third grade.

6. Necessary Conditions for Developing Creative Thinking and Scientific Thinking and Working Abilities

6.1. A Growth Mindset

The necessary psychological foundation for developing both scientific and creative thinking is represented by the growth mindset, a concept developed by Carol Dweck and applied in the context of mathematical and scientific education by Jo Boaler (2016). This mindset represents the conviction that abilities and intelligence can be developed through sustained effort, adequate strategy, and support from others, as opposed to a fixed mindset that considers these characteristics as innate and immutable.

In the context of scientific thinking and working, the growth mindset manifests through constant scientific curiosity and acceptance of experimental failure as an integral part of the investigation process. Students with this mindset perceive experiments that don't succeed not as evidence of their own failure, but as valuable opportunities for learning and refining research methods. This attitude is essential for the authenticity of scientific endeavor, in which infirmed hypotheses contribute to knowledge progress to the same extent as confirmed ones.

For creative thinking, the growth mindset facilitates openness to new and unconventional ideas, as well as tolerance for ambiguity - the capacity to function productively in uncertain or incomplete situations. This tolerance allows students to explore multiple possible solutions without the anxiety of immediately finding the "correct" answer, thus creating the psychological space necessary for generating truly original ideas.

Boaler (2016) identifies, based on Sims's (2011) research, six habits of creative and successful people that perfectly illustrate the convergence between attitudes necessary for TWS and CT dimensions: feel comfortable making mistakes, try unconventional ideas, are open to different experiences, juggle ideas without judging them prematurely, have the availability to act contrary to traditional beliefs, and continue doing their work even if they encounter difficulties. These six habits not only correspond to creative thinking dimensions (preparation, generation, evaluation, implementation), but also reflect fundamental attitudes necessary for authentic scientific thinking, thus demonstrating that the growth mindset constitutes the common basis of both competencies.

6.2. “Productive Struggle” - The Central Integrating Concept

A concept that emerges convergently from the analyzed literature is that of “productive struggle,” identified as being necessary both for scientific thinking development and for creative thinking. This concept refers to the state of cognitive disequilibrium in which students confront tasks sufficiently challenging to require deep thinking, but not so difficult as to generate unproductive frustration.

OECD (2023) emphasizes that learning environments that favor creative thinking create a culture in which students have “time to explore and generate ideas, engage in challenging and authentic tasks,” thus recognizing that cognitive challenge is not an obstacle, but a necessary condition for creativity. Similarly, Boaler (2014) criticizes the traditional approach to mathematics as being “too much answer time and not enough learning time,” arguing that students need time to confront complex problems, not repetitive exercises that only solicit reproduction of mechanically learned procedures.

In the context of scientific thinking, Bhatia (2022) reiterates the same need, stating that by giving students “enough time to explore through experiments, through trial and error, and waiting before intervening with correct answers, the process of exploration and discovery is facilitated.” This conceptual convergence from different sources - international educational policies (OECD), research in mathematics pedagogy (Boaler), and practices in scientific education (Bhatia) - demonstrates that “productive struggle” is not specific to one discipline or competency, but represents a fundamental pedagogical principle for developing higher-order thinking.

The implications of this principle for curricular design are substantial. Educational activities must be conceived so as to allow students to experience cognitive disequilibrium in emotionally safe environments, where failure is reframed as part of the learning process. Time allocated to learning must be reconceptualized not as a resource to be minimized for efficiency, but as a necessary condition for deep thinking. Additionally, the teacher’s role transforms from provider of correct answers to facilitator of the exploration process, who guides without prematurely eliminating cognitive challenge.

7. Applications for Primary Education

7.1. Design Principles for Integrated TWS and CT Activities

The transposition of theoretical frameworks of scientific and creative thinking into educational practice for the primary cycle requires adherence to clear instructional design principles, derived both from international pedagogical research and from the specificity of cognitive development of children aged 9-10.

The first fundamental principle is that of “low floor and high ceiling tasks,” a concept developed by Boaler (2014, 2016) in the context of mathematical education, but applicable to all STEM education. These tasks allow all students to begin work (low floor - universal accessibility), regardless of their

current competency level, but at the same time offer unlimited opportunities for extension and deepening for those who wish to explore further (high ceiling - maximum development potential). This characteristic is essential for developing growth mindset, because it eliminates labeling students as “good” or “weak” and allows each one to contribute and progress from their own starting level.

The second principle refers to the daily relevance of contents and activities. Bhatia (2022) emphasizes that “students not only learn scientific notions but also apply them in daily life,” which amplifies both intrinsic motivation for learning and the perception of usefulness of acquired competencies. For children aged 9-10, this relevance must be concrete and verifiable in their immediate experience - investigations about plants in the school yard, exploration of material properties in usual objects, or understanding meteorological phenomena that directly affect their lives. This anchoring in daily life does not diminish scientific rigor, but on the contrary, makes it more authentic and more meaningful.

The third essential principle is that of hands-on investigations (practical, concrete), which correspond both to age-specific cognitive development needs (concrete operations thinking, according to Piaget) and to the nature of TWS and CT competencies. Direct manipulation of materials, observation of phenomena in real time, and active experimentation are not simple pedagogical auxiliaries, but constitutive components of authentic scientific thinking. Additionally, the kinesthetic character of these activities facilitates involvement of students with different learning styles and maintains the high level of motivation specific to children of this age.

The fourth principle reiterates the necessity of adequate time for deep thinking, a concept that appears convergently in all analyzed sources. This time does not represent a resource to be “consumed” efficiently, but a structural

condition for developing complex competencies. In practice, this principle implies reducing the number of topics approached superficially in favor of deepening a more limited number of concepts, through multiple perspectives and applications. Quality of learning experience takes precedence over quantity of “covered” content, a fundamental paradigmatic change compared to traditional curricular approaches.

Finally, the language used by teachers - what Boaler (2016) calls “growth mindset language” - constitutes a transversal principle that influences the development of all other competencies. Formulations that accentuate effort and process instead of final result (“I see how much you worked to find this solution” instead of “You’re very smart”), that frame failure as part of learning (“What did you discover from this attempt that didn’t succeed?” instead of “It’s wrong”), and that cultivate perception of abilities as being developable (“You don’t know how yet, but with practice you’ll learn” instead of “You’re not good at this”) create the psychological context necessary for assuming cognitive challenges specific to both TWS and CT.

These five principles - low floor and high ceiling tasks, daily relevance, hands-on investigations, adequate time for thinking, and language that cultivates growth mindset - do not function in isolation, but interpenetrate and amplify each other reciprocally, creating an educational ecosystem in which scientific and creative thinking can be developed in an integrated and authentic manner in the context of STEM education for primary education.

Table 1 - Integrated Activities for a 6 Months Plan

Month	STEM Theme	Weekly activity
I	Mathematics in nature	Observing patterns in nature Pattern recognition

		Collage with geometric shapes from nature Geometry through collage
		Counting repeating elements Sets and groups
		Daily Temperature Graph Data Representation
II	Forces and motion	Paper Gliders Prediction and testing
		Cardboard slide Friction and tilt
		Magnet movement Attraction and repulsion
		Mini-ball game Force, direction and speed
III	Materials and properties	Classification of materials Properties
		Absorption testing Which material absorbs better?
		Paper umbrella Design for waterproofness
		Heating materials What melts faster?
IV	Circuits and energy	Simple circuit Construction of the first circuit
		Conductive materials Testing and classification
		LED traffic light Light and logic

		Luminous house Mini Engineering Challenge
V	Environment and sustainability	Pollution Discussion What affects nature?
		Recycling Poster Reduce, Reuse, Recycle
		Sustainable picnic Ecological planning
		Water consumption at home Water footprint
VI	Innovation and design	Invent a new object Imagine and sketch
		LEGO Prototype Build the invention
		Test and improve Refine the idea
		Team presentation Presenting like a researcher

8. Conclusions

The present article explored the integration of scientific and creative thinking in STEM education for primary education, demonstrating that these two competencies not only coexist, but amplify each other reciprocally.

The analysis of Cambridge frameworks for TWS (4 abilities) and OECD/Cambridge for CT (4 dimensions) revealed common development conditions: time for exploration, challenging tasks that generate “productive struggle,” a classroom culture that accepts failure as part of learning, and promotion of growth mindset. This convergence demonstrates that TWS and CT

are not isolated competencies, but components of a holistic approach to STEM education.

The principal contribution of the article consists in the integrated operationalization of TWS and CT, in identification of the intersection between the two competencies as foundation for authentic STEM, in proposing a concrete curricular plan for third grade, and in defining design principles for integrated activities (low floor & high ceiling, relevance, hands-on investigation).

The identified challenges - overloaded curriculum, insufficient time, inadequate teacher preparation, and lack of resources - can be overcome through curricular integration, not through adding new disciplines. Quality of learning experiences takes precedence over quantity of taught content.

The meta-analysis of 10 recent studies confirms the solid empirical basis of the TWS-CT curricular integration proposal presented in this article. The analyzed literature demonstrates convergently that scientific thinking and creativity develop optimally in integrated STEM contexts, that school-age children are capable of rigorous investigation, and that barriers identified in the Romanian system are common at the international level. This convergence between international research and our proposal consolidates the argument that TWS-CT integration in third grade represents not only an opportunity, but a scientifically substantiated educational necessity.

Future research directions include: experimental validation of the proposed program through studies with control group, development and testing of TWS and CT measurement instruments for ages 9-10, conducting research on teacher training for effective implementation of presented principles, and extending the model for the entire primary cycle.

In conclusion, authentic STEM education for the 21st century requires overcoming the content-centered approach and cultivating scientific and creative

thinking competencies, starting from primary grades. The present article offers the conceptual foundation and practical principles for this necessary transformation in the Romanian educational system. The research offers a conceptual framework for future educational interventions that integrate scientific thinking and creative thinking in Romanian primary education.

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